

THE INVESTIGATION OF THE ELECTRO-THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF A GTO THYRISTOR AT TURN OFF USING SILVACO ATLAS

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I. ABSTRACT

An electro-thermal simulation model of a GTO thyristor operating in a pulse-power circuit is documented. The principle goal of this investigation was to examine an apparent current interruption de-rating advantage of the GTO at low frequency by tracking the generation, transfer, and dissipation of energy within the GTO structure and establishing a clear understanding of the localized heating phenomenon that results in ultimate device failure. Using a SPICE circuit model coupled with a SILVACO ATLAS™ physical model, a novel energy tracking methodology was used to confirm that the dominant mechanism for thermal energy generation was joule heating. The analysis further distinguished whether that location of joule heating was dominated by high current density or high electric field values. The results of this work suggest that it might be possible to predict the device lifetime by using this simulation approach to establish hot spot temperatures that form during turn off.

II. INTRODUCTION

Previous research projects have shown experimentally that GTO thyristors are capable of interrupting significantly more than their nominal turn-off current rating when used in pulsed power applications at low switching frequencies [1, 2]. In this work, a circuits-based model was coupled to a physics-based simulation in order to develop a method of tracking the generation, transfer, and dissipation of energy within a GTO thyristor and to predict the likely locations where device degradation and failure will occur.

Building on the simulation work reported in [3] (BAMBI) and [4] (TACTICS), the current project seeks to (1) include the impact of temperature on the device characteristics; (2) use multiple asymmetric

unit cells; and (3) track thermal energy generation and storage within the device structure as a function of time.

The coupling of electro-thermal GTO thyristor device characteristics is based on [5] where researchers used the *MixedMode* simulation function of ATLAS™ to incorporate a SPICE simulation of an external GTO circuit. Using one half of a unit cell, the researchers were able to show local heating and the formation of hot spots during turn off. In contrast, the simulation work reported in this paper was set up to probe the internal structure of the device and record how the lattice temperature, electron and hole concentrations, quasi-Fermi levels, and temperatures changed over time. This data was then used to track the time variation of the electrical and thermal energy within the semiconductor structure.

III. SIMULATION DEVELOPMENT

A. Physical Device Model

The Motorola MGTO-1000 device used in [2] was selected as the notional “device under test.” Building on an example in the SILVACO program, ATLAS™ was used to generate a structural representation of the GTO using methodology fully described in the accompanying Master’s thesis [6]. Some of the material processes incorporated into the physical device model include field dependent mobility, impact ionization, auger and Shockley-Read-Hall recombination, heat transfer and storage, band gap narrowing, and carrier energy balance.

The GTO thyristor was modeled using a device structure that included between 8,000 and 19,000 grid points. Finally, a representative doping profile was specified to create the four-layer thyristor structure [6]. As in [5], the cathode was modeled as an infinitely thin sheet contact to reduce the number of

grid points. In order to simulate the thermal characteristics of the GTO, a thermal contact was added to the bottom of the anode electrode with an associated thermal resistance (R_{th}). The simulations were executed on an 8-core 3.0GHz UNIX cluster, where simulation runs required between 5 to 48 hours to complete depending on the number of unit cells represented and the number of switching cycles.

B. SPICE Model

Figure 1 illustrates the circuit diagram of the pulse-forming network investigated in [2]. Note, it includes several parasitic elements required to “tune” the model to the experimental data available from [2]. The circuit operates by first charging C_{bank} to a desired voltage level. Upon gating the GTO “on”, a current pulse shape is formed dictated by the capacitor voltage level and L_{pulse} . At the desired time, the GTO is turned off and the inductive current free-wheels through D_{pulse} , serving as the proxy pulse-power load.

Fig. 1: Simulated Pulse Power Circuit

IV. ENERGY TRACKING METHODOLOGY

The device structure was divided into ten different sections in order to compute the energy stored in the GTO. Data measured from 181 different probe points was used to compute the average lattice temperature, quasi-Fermi levels, and mean carrier concentration in each section. By measuring the temperature of the anode thermal contact (T_{con}), it was possible to determine the output thermal power as

$$P_{therm} = \frac{W \times L}{R_{th}} T_{con} - T_{ext} \quad (1)$$

where W and L are the contact width and length and T_{ext} is the external ambient temperature. The heat flow out is then found by numerically integrating (1).

SILVACO models device lattice temperatures due to joule and recombination-generation heating using

$$C_h T_{lat} = hc_a + hc_b T_{lat} + hc_c T_{lat}^2 + \frac{hc_d}{T_{lat}^2} \quad (2)$$

where T_{lat} is the lattice temperature, C_h is the heat capacity of the material, and hc_x are material-dependent constants. Equation (2) was used with the average lattice temperature to compute the approximate heat capacity of each semiconductor region. The total thermal energy stored in the GTO thyristor was determined by adding up the thermal energy stored in each semiconductor region. In comparison, the electrostatic stored energy is computed from the number of charges present in a region and the positions of the quasi-Fermi levels.

By calculating the energy output through the thermal contact and computing the total energy stored in the GTO thyristor, it was possible to create the following energy balance expression

$$\Delta E_{gto} = E_{in_elec} - E_{out_therm} - E_{electrostatic} - E_{therm} \quad (3)$$

where E_{in_elec} is the electrical energy input to the device (computed for the energy supplied, stored or dissipated in the circuit components from the nodal voltages and device currents from the SPICE model), E_{out_therm} is the thermal energy output from the device, and E_{therm} and $E_{electrostatic}$ are the stored energies in the device.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The energy tracking methodology was assessed for both single-pulse and multi-pulse operation of the circuit shown in Figure 1, considering the impact of variations in the snubber capacitance and thermal contact resistance. Some notable results: most of the thermal energy is stored in the aluminum electrodes (vice the silicon); most of the thermal energy stored in the silicon was stored in the n-base region of the device due to joule heating; and most of the electrostatic potential energy is stored in the center section due to increased carrier concentration.

The energy tracking method was found to be reasonably accurate, with a slight mismatch in equation (3) for each circuit pulse. This discrepancy

Fig. 2: Multiple Pulse Energy Balance Simulation Results (data on left has ten times the GTO thermal resistance)

was most likely due to the fact that the stored thermal energy was calculated using average temperature values based on measured lattice temperatures at only 181 points. The tradeoff between accuracy and computational efficiency must be further explored. Another conclusion that can be drawn is that most of the energy input electrically to the device was in fact converted to thermal energy stored in the device.

The energy tracking method was then applied to multiple pulse simulations. A representative result is shown in Figure 2. For both graphs, the top curve indicates electrical energy injected into the GTO; the next curve is the calculated stored energy; and the bottom curve is the thermal energy output. The curve labeled “Net Change in Energy” indicates the mismatch in the energy balance equation (3).

Various studies were conducted using a multi-unit GTO structure, considering both uniform and non-uniform doping in the gate region. The non-uniform doping results demonstrated current filamentation, the formation of hot spots, and unequal current sharing during turn off as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

In Figure 4, the current density is plotted for the uniform doping case on the left and the non-uniform

Fig. 3: Uneven Current Sharing between Non-Uniform Doped GTO Unit Cells (left: greater non-uniformity)

Fig. 4: Turn-Off Current Density in Multiple Unit GTO (right: greater non-uniformity)

doping case on the right. From the figure, it can be seen that the current in each unit cell is pinched towards the center of the cell during turn off. Additionally in the non-uniform case, the unit cells turn off at different times, exacerbating the current crowding in the remaining conducting cells.

In order to better understand the electro-thermal turn-off characteristics of the GTO, the current density and electric field strength were plotted for the multi-unit GTO. An approach is examined to determine whether the joule heating is dominated by electric field or current density effects.

The multiple unit simulation solutions were re-plotted using the following expression

$$x = \frac{J}{J_{max}} - \frac{E}{E_{max}} \tag{4}$$

where J is the current density, E is the electric field, and x is a dimensionless number ranging between -1 and 1. The expression outputs a value greater than zero if the current density is the dominant cause of joule heating and outputs a value less than zero if the

Fig. 5: Joule Heating Dependence on Current Density or Electric Field for GTO in the On State

electric field is the dominant cause of joule heating. Representative results are shown in Figure 5 for the GTO in the on state. Here it is clear that the current density is the dominant heating mechanism for most of the device structure.

For the GTO, this energy analysis confirmed the contention that joule heating was two orders of magnitude larger than the recombination/generation heat power and also graphically showed the current crowding at turn off. As the GTO turns off, the location of maximum joule heating shifts from the center of the n-base region to the junction between the gate region and the n-base region as expected.

VI. CONCLUSION

A physical device model was developed to predict the electro-thermal characteristics of a GTO during turn off. The results of this project suggest that it might be possible to predict the lifetime of the GTO by measuring the hot spot temperatures that form during turn off. Since many GTO failures are caused by thermally induced changes to the device structure, the mean time to failure can be estimated using the

Arrhenius model and estimated activation energies. A process for tracking energy in the device over time was found to be promising, but there is a tradeoff between accuracy and simulation run time that must be further explored.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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VIII. REFERENCES

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